

Detection of Free Radicals produced during the Photolysis of Potassium Hexachloroiridate(IV) in Organic Solution

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The mechanisms of thermal redox reactions of various organic substrates with different metal ions were best explained by the free radical formation in the intermediate stages. However, the formation of free radicals in these reactions was generally supported by the induced polymerisation reaction of acryl nitrile. Electron paramagnetic resonance technique of spin trapping¹ has now become the method of choice for studying free radical mediated reactions at room temperature². Earlier we reported the results of the spin trapping studies of photo-oxidation reaction of various alcohols by hexachlorometallate(IV) ions (M = Pt, Pd and Ir), aldehydes and ketones by hexachloropalladate(IV) and -iridate(IV) ions and monosaccharides by hexachloroiridate(IV) ions³. In these preliminary studies, it was observed that under identical experimental condition, the hexachloroiridate(IV) ions were more versatile photo-oxidant than either hexachloroplatinate(IV) or -palladate(IV) ions. In this communication some initial spin trapping results of the detection of free radical produced

during the photolysis of hexachloroiridate(IV) ions in presence of some organic substrates such as acetic acid, glycine, alanine, formamide, dimethyl formamide and acetonitrile in neat and aqueous solutions (50%), are reported.

Results and Discussion

The expected free radicals produced in these photo-redox reactions are trapped by the diamagnetic scavengers (spin traps) to form epr detectable spin adducts which exhibit characteristic epr spectra. In this study nitron spin traps were preferred over nitroso spin traps because of their photostabilities in these experimental conditions. The characteristic epr spectrum (Fig. 1) of resulting nitroxide (spin adduct) (equation 3) is dominated by the triplet signal due to ¹⁴N and the secondary doublet due to β-hydrogen. The coupling constants of the epr spectra obtained in these different photo-redox reactions with different organic substrates are summarised in Table 1. The magnitudes of these para-

TABLE 1—HYPERFINE SPLITTING CONSTANTS OF SPIN ADDUCTS

Organic substrate	Radical trapped	Hyperfine splitting constants (mT)			
		(a) PBN		(b) SPBN*	
		a _N	a _H	a _N	a _H
CH ₃ COOH	*CH ₂ COOH	1.42	0.32	1.51	0.61
CH ₂ (NH ₂)COOH	*CH(NH ₂)COOH	—	—	1.52	0.60
CH ₃ CH(NH ₂)COOH	*CH ₂ CH(NH ₂)COOH	—	—	1.50	0.62
HCONH ₂	*CONH ₂	1.45	0.31	1.52	0.59
HCON(CH ₃) ₂	*CON(CH ₃) ₂	1.40	0.38	1.51	0.61
CH ₃ CN	*CH ₂ CN	1.38	0.39	1.51	0.62

*SPBN spin trap was used in 50% aqueous solutions.

Fig. 1. EPR spectrum of spin adduct of $\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CN}$ with SPBN obtained on the photolysis of (IrCl_6^{2-}) in 50% aqueous solution of CH_3CN

eters suggest the trapping of carbon centred free radicals formed in these reactions⁴. This can be explained by the reaction of photoexcited hexachloroiridate(IV) with C-H bond of the organic substrates followed by hydrogen abstraction. The free radical thus formed then reacts with spin trapping agent (PBN/SPBN) to form respective spin adducts (equations 1-3).

where R is the remaining part of the organic substrate. It is interesting to note that the photolysis of $(\text{AsPh}_4)_2\text{IrCl}_6$ in CH_3CN yielded Cl^\bullet adduct of PBN with coupling constants in excellent agreement with those reported in the earlier study⁵ and the addition

of small quantity (ca 1%) of water to CH_3CN solution prior to photolysis resulted into the production of $\cdot\text{OH}$ adduct due to the hydrolysis of Cl^\bullet adduct^{3,5}. But in the present study, the photolysis of Na_2IrCl_6 in CH_3CN yielded the spin adduct of $\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CN}$ with PBN and also with SPBN when 50% aqueous solution was used. This can be attributed to nucleophilic reaction of Cl^\bullet adduct with substrate and also to the preference for the direct interaction with the photo-excited hexachloroiridate(IV) ions (equation 2). The formation of carbon centred radical, $\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CN}$ in preference to Cl^\bullet in the present study was further confirmed by wide-band photolysis of sodium hexachloroiridate(IV) solution in CH_3CN at 77 K. The resulting epr spectrum (Fig. 2) clearly showed a prominent intense triplet ($a_{\text{H}} = 1.93$ mT at $g = 2.00$) indicating the trapping of $\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CN}$ in the organic glass.

Thus these results indicate the formation of mainly the carbon-centred radicals by hydrogen abstraction process in these photo-redox reactions.

Experimental

The details of the epr technique of spin trapping

NOTE

Fig. 2. EPR spectrum of CH_2CN obtained on the photolysis of (IrCl_6^{2-}) in CH_3CN glass at 77 K.

are the same as described earlier³. α -Phenyl-*N*-t-butyl nitron (PBN) and sodium 2-sulphenatophenyl-t-butyl nitron (2-SPBN) (Aldrich) were used as spin trapping agents in the neat and aqueous organic solutions respectively. 18-Crown-6 was used to solubilise the hexachloroiridate(IV) salt in neat organic substrate solutions. Other organic substrates (solvents) were of extra pure/spectroscopic grade.

The photolysis was done by using 100/200 W Hg/Xe high pressure point sources lamps, the output of which was filtered through wide-band interference filter (380–440 nm). For cryogenic work, a 1000 W Hg/Xe point source was used, the output of which was filtered through a UG-5 broad-band interference filter immersed in circulating water. Control experiments were performed without inorganic salt to ensure that there is no epr signal due to direct photolysis of either the organic substrates or spin trapping agents (SPBN/PBN) under the experimental conditions.

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